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Using CO₂ Concentration level and Motion IoT Sensors to Generate Internal Gains Profiles and Use Them in Buildings Energy Modelling to Create Physics-Based Digital Twins

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Abstract:

The accuracy of calibrated buildings' energy models what is called Physics-based Digital Twins (DT) is vitally important to reach accurate models. Having internal gains profiles that represent the actual operation of the building during the period being calibrated will be reflected in the simulation result as a more accurate replication of the physical asset compared to real measurements. The DT can then be used to test scenarios and their impacts on the IEQ and energy consumption. This paper suggests a new approach to generating internal gains profiles using historical CO₂ level and motion sensor data to determine the occupancy at each time. Also, the generated profile can then be used to create other modulating profiles such as equipment loads in offices. The study took an office building as an example and calibrated the energy model for CO₂ levels and air temperatures. The calibration metrics that are used to determine how accurate the model is performing compared to the real building are the Mean-Absolute-Errors (MAE) and the Root-Mean-Square-Error both showed a significant improvement with average CO₂-MAE and CO₂-RMSE lower by 26% and 23% respectively. For the air temperature, the MAE and RMSE average values were both improved by 13%.

Keywords

Building Calibration, Internal gains profiles, Digital Twins, CO₂ sensors, Motion Sensors

Introduction

About 40% of the global energy use goes to buildings (Tricoire, 2021), therefore, it is essential to develop solutions and make use of any possible energy savings. While energy models were used only to achieve compliance, they are still valuable resources that can be enhanced and used to achieve energy savings in the built environment. Models that were used in the past and archived after that can be referred to as Sleeping Digital Twins (SDT). Those models should be awakened

through calibration to make them valid again for operational usage. Baseline energy models, using IoT can be transformed into very useful digital twins, that can be used to accurately predict energy use and find the most suitable retrofit scenarios for any building (IES, 2021).

Traditionally the occupancy is estimated based on surveys and generic operating hours of premises. This study proposes a new method to estimate occupancy using CO₂ and motion sensors as a proxy. The concept is applied to a case study on the Helix building. A two-story office building located in West Glasgow in Scotland.

Since regular energy models do not necessarily represent real-world buildings. This is mainly because of the gap usually found between the design models and the real-world building which is referred to as the Performance Gap. The energy performance gap can be defined as the difference between a building's actual energy consumption and its design performance. (CIBSE, 2020) (ASHRAE, 2014). To evaluate the energy performance of buildings there is more than one approach to modelling:

- Compliance calculation: Using a simplified approach, the model is created to comply with building regulations. This type of model cannot be used to predict the actual performance of buildings
- Design performance: This is the model which is created at the designing stage following operational energy performance protocols such as CIBSE-TM54 (CIBSE, 2022). Those are as-designed performance models and should not be confused with the as-built performance (post-construction). However, the as-designed model can be used to identify any construction issues or/and operational shortfalls.
- In-use baseline: buildings' operation might change due to a change of use or to meet new requirements. The in-use baseline is revised from a model reflecting the actual operational conditions. These conditions might change during the building's lifetime but the model would still contain all the technical design inputs. In other words, they are as-designed models but with modified operation conditions.
- Actual energy use: Metered energy use of the building during stable and steady operation, typically after at least a couple of years of occupancy. See Figure 1 for the different gaps in different types of models.

Figure 1 Different Gaps in Different Models

Some buildings might be designed for energy performance but operated for comfort. Operational energy models are useful to apply dynamic Measurement and Verifications to the building during its lifetime. An operational contains the current setup of the building systems, space types and occupancy schedules (profiles). However, to minimise the gap between the operational model and the real building measurement, the model can be calibration against the physical asset and turning it into what is known as a Physics-Based Digital Twin (PbDT), where Key data required are physical properties of the facility, equipment and system types and efficiencies, appropriate weather data, and control sequences. In addition to that internal gains should match what is in the building and should follow the same profiles.

The theory behind calibrated models is to apply changes to the design model to start behaving like the real building. This includes real data such as the proper weather file, the data from IoT sensors/smart meters and any occupancy indications such as desk/meeting room booking systems. Once the data is available, the process of developing and validating the calibrated energy simulation models can be started. Assessment of building operation and performance once occupied is important to know if there are any problems with a building and establish potential solutions. Measurement and Verification (M&V) is a process within which planning, measuring, collecting, and analysing of knowledge is undertaken and then reporting the performance of the building.

Building Dynamic Simulation:

The dynamic simulation of buildings is necessary to put the building under test in a variable environment similar to the one under which the building will be operated in real-life.

The flexibility in the dynamic simulation tool inputs where setpoints, internal gains, hot water temperatures, fan speeds and other building variables can be fed to the model as custom profiles is vitally important to the calibration process in general and for the approach used in this research in particular.

Those custom profiles (also known as Free-Form-Profiles) can either be absolute or modulating values that are created externally or within the simulation tool. Such capabilities allow feeding the real data (BMS, IoT, Energy bills ...etc) to the model. The real data help reduce the gap between the simulation results and the real-world building measurement and give more accurate models for Measurements and Verification analysis

The International Performance Measurement and Verification Protocol (IPMVP)

The IPMVP is a framework developed for measuring the performance in the implementation of energy conservation measures (ECMs) (EVO, 2016). It provides guidelines and boundaries for measurements, measurement periods, and methods of calculating the savings and performing operational verification. There are some options to calculate the impact of ECMs depending on the type and its relation with other building performance inputs or outputs:

- *Option 1:* retrofit isolation, key parameter measurement
- *Option 2:* retrofit isolation, all parameter measurement

- *Option 3*: whole-facility
- *Option 4*: calibrated simulation

For each option, IPMVP indicates the data required in addition to the monitoring and measurement protocols. It also provides suggestions on ways to perform accurate calculations and validate the results regarding other relevant standards and protocols (CIBSE, 2020).

IPMVP Option 4, calibrated simulation, suggests the use of building performance modelling tools to calculate the energy consumption and stimulate the demand, which is to be calibrated with hourly or monthly utility billing data. The framework explains in a step-by-step a method to fine-tune the model to reflect the building and its real operating conditions more accurately in relevance to ASHRAE Guideline 14: *Measurement of Energy, Demand and Water Savings* (ASHRAE, 2014) for criteria to check calibration accuracy either at hourly or at monthly intervals. Detailed operational information should be collected during site surveys. and by measurements to calibrate the model.

Once calibration is reached, we can use the model to track deviations in the operation of the building and investigate the root causes. Moreover, Physics-based Digital Twins (PBDT) are now used in testing what-if scenarios and studying the impact of suggested changes in the operation of the building (changing setpoints, reducing the occupancy...etc) or the use of new technology such as energy storage, solar panels or smart shading devices. However, calibration is not an easy thing to achieve. In the past, the calibration process was an art form that inevitably relied on user knowledge, experience, statistical expertise, technical judgment, and a great deal of trial and error (Sustainable Places, 2022). However, with the introduction of cloud-based services and advanced computer technology, we can now easily do hundreds of simulations for a model until a minimal error is reached compared to the physical asset. In buildings, this is more challenging, especially if we have complex geometry or/and complex patterns of use. For example, the COVID-19 pandemic helped many companies to embrace hybrid working and hot desk booking systems, as much as these new measures arguably help maintain better work environments, it puts lots of challenges to buildings' energy modelling. This is mainly because the building is no longer operated in fixed weekly patterns (profiles). The occupancy schedule of a particular day in the week might not match one of the weeks before. This can put challenges when simulations are done to work out things like energy predictions.

The internal gains profiles are usually built based on standardised patterns for the space type such as the profiles from the National Calculation Methodology (NCM, 2021). However, those profiles are assumptions from studies that were done on spaces with similar applications and do not necessarily represent the spaces in the building. They are good for design purposes but not for measurement and verification analysis.

This study suggests a new approach to estimating the occupancy of a working space using the historical data from a typical operation year and the current readings. The building to which the approach was applied is the Helix building which is a two-story office building located in West Glasgow in the United Kingdom. Figures 2(a) and 2(b) show the building in real life and the geometry that was used in the simulation respectively.

Figure 2(a) A Picture of The Helix Building – West Glasgow

Figure 2(b) Helix Building Model

Methodology

The first step to reaching a PbDT is to have an initial model. The best practice for this would be a design model as it contains as many details as possible of the building and the systems. The next step is to feed the correct weather file of the year against which we intend to calibrate the model. We can then run an initial simulation to compare the current status of the model and how far are the results from the real data. The profiles in the model should then be replaced with real data profiles and this process is repeated for different parameters in the model until calibration is reached. Figure 3 simplifies the best practice for the calibration process.

Figure 3: Best Practice for Energy Models Calibration

Historical CO2 Levels Data

The concept of this approach is to build up-on IoT sensor data, mainly CO2 concentration levels and motion sensors. The study suggests a new method to estimate the occupancy of a working space using historical data from a typical operation year and past/current readings. The data that were used are CO2 concentration levels and motion sensors. The CO2 levels are to be overlapped for summer and winter seasons separately after excluding the weekends. This way we can analyse the CO2 levels inside the room, considering that people would normally open the windows more frequently during the summertime the thing which allows for more natural ventilation. This natural ventilation impacts the peak CO2 level when the space is fully occupied.

In this study, a sophisticated data analysis tool was used to collect and analyse the historical IoT sensors data, then the daily measurements for the CO2 levels were

overlaid to have a better understanding of its link to the density of occupancy. Figure 4 displays the visualisation of the CO2 levels (overlaid) in an open space office on the ground floor of the Helix building, during the period from May-Dec 2019.

Figure 4 An overlay of the CO2 levels for an open space office (May-Dec 2019)

This Overlay has no clear patterns of CO2 and cannot help analyse the occupancy unless it is divided into summer and winter periods. Figures 5 and 6 show the overlaid CO2 readings for summer and winter accordingly after dividing the analysis period into two (May-Sep) and (Oct-Dec). This will allow for the higher natural ventilation during the summer to be accounted for. Also, the weekends were discarded to see the patterns of the CO2 levels more clearly.

Figure 5 An overlay of the CO2 levels during the summer period (2019)

Figure 6 An overlay of the CO2 levels during the winter period (2019)

A linear equation is solved using the two points that represent the maximum and the minimum occupancy in the space. Those values are dependent on a parameter such as the permeability of the space fabrics, the type/quality of the windows and the frequency at which they are opened, and the total volume and the maximum capacity of the space. Therefore, it is better to take the values for each space independently when the data is available. See Figure 7 for the linear equations representing the initial modulating profile for the occupancy.

Each equation can give an output from 0 to 1, there will be CO2 concentration levels that will produce values out of these boundaries, for such values they will be considered as 1 (if >1) or 0 (if <0).

Figure 7 Linear equation representation of CO2 levels in an open space office in the Helix building taken from a typical year (2019)

The CO2 level unfortunately does not drop instantly when occupants leave the place for breaks during the day. To account for that, motion sensors were used to govern

the equation (i.e. when there no motion put zero occupancies no matter how much is the CO2 concentration level). This will account for unoccupied hours, lunch breaks and anytime the room is not occupied. This is also useful when used in meeting rooms to give an estimation of the room occupied times across.

Generating Occupancy Profiles

The Dynamic Simulation for the building was carried out using IES-VE (IES, 2021). Two simulations were carried out, once with generic profiles from The National Calculation Methodology (NCM, 2021), and once again using the CO2/motion sensors driven profiles and the results were compared. The generic occupancy profiles for open-space offices and meeting rooms are shown in figures 8(a) & 8(b). For other internal loads, a simple profile was used (from 8:00 am to 6:00 pm)

Figure 8(a) Occupancy profile for office spaces taken from NCM

Figure 8(b) Occupancy profile for meeting rooms taken from NCM

For the second simulation, the profiles were created in an external data analysis tool with the help of the IoT sensors. This can also be achieved using a python script with an appropriate output file format. The Expression that was used to build the occupancy profile followed the statements below:

Calculate the occupancy level (0 to 1) based on the linear equation obtained from the CO2 levels concentration overlaid values.

If the resulted profile point is higher than (1) the modulating profile should return the value 1, and 0 if it's lower than 0.

The equation will apply only if the timestamp lies within the occupied hours, and the motion sensor was active at any point of the current 10 minutes time window.

The generated occupancy profile using this approach will be variable based on the CO2 levels in that particular room. Figure 9 shows an example of the resulting profile for a week in January 2020 before the COVID-19 pandemic. Figure 10 shows the same profile plotted for the period January – Nov 2020. Where the lockdown periods were cleared reflected in the profile from mid-March to August.

Note: The occupancy profile also reflects the reduced occupancy due to the social measures that took place post-pandemic.

Figure 9 a Week of the generated Occupancy profile for an open space office (13-19 January 2020) during normal operation of the building (pre-pandemic)

Figure 10 Eleven months plot (Jan-Nov) 2020 of the generated Occupancy profile for an open space office Showing the changes in the pattern of the occupancy when the lockdown was imposed in the 2nd quarter of the year

Results and Analysis

The simulation was run with both the generic and CO2-driven profiles. The calibrated model using the CO2 driven profiles opened the doors to calibrate the model against other IEQ parameters not only the indoor temperature. In this study, the CO2 concentration levels were calibrated for different rooms. This model is therefore suitable to be used to evaluate what-if scenarios that impact indoor air quality while maintaining comfort and saving. Table 1 shows the improvement in the CO2 levels

calibration metrics in different spaces when using the profiles generated from the CO2 and the motion sensors.

Space Name	ISCAN Channel	Generic Profiles		CO2 Driven Profiles		RMSE improvement	MAE improvement
		CO2 Calibration Metrics		CO2 Calibration Metrics			
		RMSE	MAE	RMSE	MAE		
OpenSpaceOffice01	SC000084	250.6	208.1	223.9	181.5	-26.6	-26.5
MeetingRoom1	SC000012	303.8	275.3	242.7	196.8	-61.1	-78.5
OpenSpaceOffice00.1	SC000018	123.5	152.3	99.0	109.5	-24.5	-42.8
MeetingRoom2	SC000024	237.3	237.9	328.6	252.0	91.3	14.1
OpenSpaceOffice00.2	SC000030	159.4	157.7	98.3	106.8	-61.1	-50.8
MeetingRoom3	SC000036	435.6	336.7	500.8	348.7	65.2	12.0
Kitchen00	SC000042	209.5	196.7	254.3	179.9	44.8	-16.8
MeetingRoom4	SC000048	382.3	307.3	364.6	273.9	-17.7	-33.4
MeetingRoom7	SC000078	292.4	258.2	233.8	186.7	-58.7	-71.4
MeetingRoom5	SC000054	Data gaps	Data gaps	Data gaps	Data gaps	N/A	N/A
OpenSpaceOffice00.3	SC000066	170.1	163.7	94.5	106.8	-75.6	-56.8
MeetingRoom6	SC000072	306.5	277.5	241.8	193.3	-64.7	-84.2

Table 1 CO2 Levels RMSE and MAE improvement

Note: For the kitchen and the meeting rooms (2, 3 and 5) CO2 sensors encountered lots of data gaps during the measured period, thus it should be discarded from the results.

Figures 11(a) and 11(b) compare the calibration metrics for the CO2 concentration levels for the two simulation results

Figure 11(a) CO2 Metrics When Using Generic Profiles

Figure 11(b) CO2 Metrics When Using CO2 Driven Profiles

Figure 12 compare the two simulation results for CO2 levels for a full week on March 2020 (the 3rd week) including the day on the first covid-19 lockdown was imposed. See how the simulation results matches the measured CO2 level concentration in [PPM] for both days with normal occupancy levels and the days that had less occupancy or zero occupancy.

Figure 12 Indoor CO2 Level Concentration an open space office Simulation with Generic Profiles (Orange), Simulation with CO2 Driven Profiles (Blue) and Measurement (Green), 3rd week of March 2020

Table 2 shows the improvement in the CO2 levels calibration metrics in different spaces when using the profiles generated from the CO2 and the motion sensors.

Space Name	ISCAN Channel	Generic Profiles		CO2 Driven Profiles		RMSE improvement	MAE improvement
		Temp Calibration Metrics		Temp Calibration Metrics			
		RMSE	MAE	RMSE	MAE		
OpenSpace Office01	SC0000 79	0.839	0.667	0.703	0.558	-0.136	-0.109
MeetingRoom m1	SC0000 07	1.035	0.807	0.961	0.716	-0.074	-0.091
OpenSpace Office00.1	SC0000 13	0.925	0.761	0.736	0.585	-0.188	-0.176
MeetingRoom m2	SC0000 19	1.229	0.953	1.167	0.906	-0.062	-0.047
OpenSpace Office00.2	SC0000 25	0.952	0.735	0.902	0.731	-0.050	-0.004
MeetingRoom m3	SC0000 31	1.795	1.459	1.672	1.349	-0.123	-0.110
Kitchen00	SC0000 37	1.174	0.931	1.080	0.879	-0.094	-0.053
MeetingRoom m4	SC0000 43	1.481	1.165	1.141	0.893	-0.340	-0.272
MeetingRoom m7	SC0000 73	1.084	0.814	0.999	0.754	-0.085	-0.060
MeetingRoom m5	SC0000 49	1.202	0.985	0.973	0.744	-0.230	-0.241
OpenSpace Office00.3	SC0000 61	1.282	1.095	0.904	0.732	-0.378	-0.363
MeetingRoom m6	SC0000 67	1.288	0.991	1.226	0.953	-0.061	-0.039

Table 2 Indoor Air Temperature RMSE and MAE improvement

Figures 13(a) and 13(b) compare the calibration metrics for the indoor air temperature concentration levels for the two simulation results.

Figure 13(a) Air Temperature Metrics When Using Generic Profiles

Figure 13(b) Air Temperature Metrics Using CO2 Driven Profiles

Figure 12 shows the plot for the indoor air temperature when using the generic profiles for the internal gains (occupancy, lighting and equipment) (in Orange), and using the CO2-driven profiles (in Blue) Vs Measurement (in Green) for the 3rd week of March 2020.

Figure 14 Indoor Air Temperatures Plot for an open space office Simulation with Generic Profiles (Orange), Simulation with CO2 Driven Profiles (Blue) and Measurement (Green), 3rd week of March 2020

Conclusion

Physics-based Digital Twins (PbDT) opened new doors to accurately simulate/test what-if scenarios for physical assets (buildings) before implementing the change in the

real life. However, the accuracy of the PbDT is vitally important for it to serve its purpose. The internal gains should be modelled to follow profiles that represent the real-world scenario as closely as possible, and in the absence of occupancy counters, it would be difficult to accurately address the issue of variant occupancy especially if the operation of the building changes. This study made use of the available CO₂ concentration levels and motion sensors to generate profiles that can be used in simulation to reach a highly calibrated model (PbDT). Lower calibration metrics (MAE and RMSE) were achieved for both indoor air temperature (13% lower) and CO₂ concentration levels (23-26% lower). For some spaces, the CO₂ data had lots of gaps and the metrics could not be calculated correctly.

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